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World Multidisciplinary Earth Sciences

Symposium

2015

save the EARTH

WMIESS 2015

Abstract Collection

Book

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Prague (Czech Republic)

Eco-friendly Symposium - WMIESS

*the more you save the Earth
the more you get wealth*

Preface

This Abstract Collection consists of the abstracts of papers presented in the “World Multidisciplinary Earth Sciences Symposium” in the city of romance Prague (Czech Republic) during 7-11 September 2015. The World Multidisciplinary Earth Sciences Symposium (WMESS) aims to provide a forum for discussion of the latest findings and technologies in different fields of Earth Sciences, to give opportunities for future collaborations. WMESS wants to be a platform for sharing knowledge and experiences in the fields of Earth Sciences, to lead for providing a forum for early career researchers for presentation of their work and discussion of their ideas with experts in different fields of Earth Sciences such as; Tectonics & Structural Geology; Engineering Geology; Geotechnics; Hydro-Hydrogeological Sciences; Natural Hazards; Geomorphology; Geochemistry, Mineralogy, Petrology & Volcanology; Stratigraphy, Sedimentology & Palaeontology; Geophysics & Seismology; Geodesy, Photogrammetry & Cartography; Informatics, Geoinformatics & Remote Sensing; Mining Engineering; Mineral Processing; Blasting & New Technologies; Natural Resources; Environmental Sciences; Energy, Resources & Pollution & the Environment; Environmental Legislation; Biogeosciences; Geological Heritage & Geoparks; Urban Planning; Atmospheric Sciences – Climate; Modelling and Soft Computing Techniques in Earth Sciences; Medical Geology; Occupational Health and Safety.

However the idea of organization of WMESS is quite old, the 1st WMESS was organized this year. WMESS 2015 will be one of the Annual series. However, nowadays there had been many local or international meetings related to Earth Sciences, we decided to organize a traditional style of symposium, friendlier and very fruitful alternative world symposium which is not a festival-like super-large convention, too chaotic and busy to have a chance to discuss something in deeper with other participants.

The main mission of the "World Multidisciplinary Earth Sciences Symposium - WMESS" is to lead to contribute in multidisciplinary studies related with atmosphere, biosphere, hydrosphere, lithosphere and pedosphere of the Earth and interaction of the human with them. As another mission, it provides a forum for this diverse range of studies, which report very latest results and document emerging understanding of the Earth's system and our place in it. The Scientific Committee and Institutional Scientific Partners of WMESS was completed by paying strict attention, and all members were selected from well-known, very much appreciated, productive and representatives of the different countries. We are deeply grateful to the members of the scientific committee and institutional scientific partners (International Association for Engineering Geology & the Environment – **IAEG**, International Union of Soil Sciences – **IUSS**, International Geographical Union – **IGU**, The International Association of Hydrogeologists – **IAH**, Geological Sciences of Italy – **SGI**, Czech Soil Science Society – **CSSS**, Arabian Geosciences Union – **ArabGU**, The Society of Economic Geology of Romania – **SEGR**, World Meteorological Organization – **WMO**, International Medical Geology Association – **IMGA**, Russian Mineralogical Society – **RMS**, University of Petrosani) of WMESS.

We would like to express our sincere gratitude to all 500+ participants of WMESS 2015 from 50+ different countries all over the world for their interests and contributions in WMESS 2015. We wish you enjoy the World Multidisciplinary Earth Sciences Symposium – WMESS 2015 and have a pleasant stay in the city of romance Prague. We hope to see you again during next event WMESS 2016 which will be held in Prague (Czech Republic) approximately in the similar period.

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President of WMESS – Chair of WMESS 2015

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Landslide susceptibility mapping based on the 2008 MORLE in Santa Catarina, Brazil

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ABSTRACT

An analysis of a multiple occurrence regional landslide event (MORLE) in the Itajaí valley (Santa Catarina State, Brazil) in November 2008 is presented. The nature of the event, its conditioning factors and the effects caused are described. Over 1500 slope movements were concentrated within an area of about 300 km², with important losses of lives and material damages. Events of a similar nature and magnitude have occurred in this state and others of southern Brazil during the last few decades. In order to assess to what extent the type and quality of data available on this event could provide the basis for prediction in the case of future events, an analysis of the relationship between landslide ruptures and conditioning factors was carried out. The approach was based on statistical correlations using an heuristic model, relying to a great extent on expert judgements, derived from the experience acquired during field surveys carried out after the event. A susceptibility model was thus obtained, and it was validated using different strategies. The output of the former model was compared with the one of more objective models, based on Favourability Functions. The results show that useful predictions can be made with the amount and type of information available. There are no time series on landslide occurrence in the area and therefore hazard maps (expressed in terms of probability) could not be obtained, but susceptibility assessments coupled with data on population centres and damage information provided the basis for a preliminary risk analysis. The methodology used and results obtained are presented and discussed.

Key words: Landslide susceptibility; model validation; MORLE; Santa Catarina (Brazil).

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Sinkhole collapse hazard in the Camargo valley (northern Spain)

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ABSTRACT

The municipality of Camargo (Cantabria, northern Spain), is an area where dominate the calcareous materials (Aptian age), constituting an intensely karstified relief crossed by a network of underground galleries that allow water circulation. This area is frequently affected by cover collapse sinkholes, called locally *soplaos*, which affect buildings, infrastructures and terrain properties producing significant economic losses and social concern. The work aims to develop tools to predict the areas prone to collapse, in order to reduce damage, as well as to improve our knowledge on these processes in a calcareous karst context. A data base has been constructed in a GIS, including the 88 inventoried collapses and 11 data layers representing the conditioning factors of the process; these layers have been selected by visual analysis, a principal component analysis and the comparative study of validation rate curves that best explain the sinkholes occurrences. Several sinkhole susceptibility models have been produced by means of spatial data analysis techniques (favourability functions and simple spatial statistics) and using different variable combinations on the basis of principal component analysis. From the independent evaluation, all models show a good prediction capability when 5 (lithology, elevation, rivers distance, roads distance and buildings distance) or more variables are used. According to the results, sinkhole processes in the study area are strongly related to the proximity of fluvial channels. Models obtained are useful to identify areas where mitigation efforts will be most cost-effective. They allow identifying priority areas for the implementation of actions to reduce vulnerability (elements) or hazard (processes). Also, the procedure can be used as a preventive tool, through its application to Strategic Environmental Impact Assessment (SEIA) of land use plans.

Key words: Collapse sinkholes; subsidence hazard; prediction modeling and validation; northern Spain.

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Landslide hazard and risk scenarios development (LAHARS project)

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ABSTRACT

This project intends to develop a set of methods and techniques to design landslide hazard and risk scenarios, with the aim of making better predictions to reduce the risk due to this type of process. The approach is founded on the hypothesis that it is possible to conceive those scenarios on the basis of a detailed knowledge on landslides occurred in the recent past, their causes and consequences. Hazard predictions, as any hypothesis on the future behaviour of the processes, must be based on several assumptions materialized in what is commonly termed scenarios. It is necessary to obtain long series of past landslide occurrences to deal with cause-effect relationships between landslides and triggering factors (precipitation, seismicity, human activity on the basis of the analysis of sedimentation rates and coastal erosion), in order to define hazard scenarios by extrapolating into the future. These hazard scenarios, which will not be only based on the uniformitarian assumption *sensu stricto*, will be proposed either directly, through extrapolation from observed trend of past landslide occurrences, or indirectly from the return period of the triggering factors. Risk scenarios and models, based on the previous hazard models, will also integrate estimates on vulnerability and exposure. This will make the development of quantitative prediction models for landsliding possible. Afterwards, the risk models obtained will be validated in order to know the prediction capability. Moreover, the prediction improvement will contribute to reduce the economic losses due to this type of process and to better develop land planning and management. On the other hand, cost/benefit analyses will be accomplished by comparing risk models with and without mitigation measures. The investigation is being carried out in western Guipúzcoa (northern Spain) where different types of mass movements will be analysed, mainly shallow slides and flows. The results will improve the understanding of slope processes, their occurrence, activity and their relationships with their principal triggering factors, which will benefit landslide hazard and risk assessment and mapping, facilitating a better anticipation and matching of the society in a context of Global Change.

Key words: Landslides; triggering factors; risk scenarios; susceptibility and hazard models.

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